

A sensitivity analysis of some SPERT-III E-core experiments with ANTARES v1.0

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ABSTRACT

A sensitivity analysis has been performed on a selection of the SPERT-III E reactivity accident tests with the multi-physics numerical platform ANTARES. The objective is to evaluate the influence of data uncertainties and effective temperature models on the simulated power transient. This analysis emphasizes the importance of accurately determining the initial position of control rods, given the strong sensitivity of the power peak to the transient rod worth. Furthermore, both the experimental uncertainty associated with the initial reactivity insertion (linked to the transient rod worth and position) and the modeling uncertainty of the effective fuel temperature can significantly affect the results. This work represents a first step in the interpretation of SPERT-III experiments, contributing to the validation of ANTARES v1.0—a coupled multi-physics simulation code developed by ASNR—for fast transient analyses.

Keywords: ANTARES, Rod Ejection Accident, SPERT, sensitivity

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the French Authority for Nuclear Safety and Radiation Protection (ASNR), following the Institute for Radiological Protection and Nuclear Safety (IRSN), has developed the coupled multi-physics simulation tool ANTARES v1.0 [1], which integrates the 3D core neutronics code PARCS with the system thermal-hydraulics code CATHARE-3. ANTARES is designed to support nuclear safety studies under both steady-state and transient conditions.

The validation of ANTARES proceeds in two phases. The first phase focused on the Watts Bar benchmark [2], addressing steady-state and fuel-cycle computations [3], while the second phase extends the validation to fast transients using SPERT experiments [4][5]. Following the good results obtained for the first one [3], ANTARES can now be confidently applied to the analysis of SPERT transients. This paper presents a sensitivity analysis of selected SPERT-III E-core accident tests, using a cross-section library and PARCS input deck kindly provided by the University of Michigan (2 energy groups, ENDF/B-VII). Two tests are considered: Test 60 (initiated from very low power) and Test 86 (initiated at 100% nominal power). The study evaluates the impact of uncertainties in input data and effective temperature models on the simulation results. Particular attention is given to the computation of control rod positions, due to the strong sensitivity of the power peak to the transient rod worth.

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Following a brief description of the SPERT program (Section 2), of ANTARES multi-physics platform (Section 3) and the methodology (Section 4), the analyses for the two selected experiments are presented (Sections 5 and 6), and the main conclusions are summarized in Section 7.

2. SPERT PROGRAM

SPERT-III E (Special Power Excursion Reactor Tests, E-core) [4 and 5] comprises a series of experimental reactivity accident tests conducted in the 1960s on a small, pressurized water reactor (PWR) loaded with oxide fuel and operated under conditions representative of a typical PWR. This program remains one of the few experimental references for fast transient behavior in PWRs, in which the main feedback mechanism limiting the power excursion is the Doppler effect. Reactivity is introduced through the ejection of a cruciform-shaped central absorbing rod, and the principal measured quantity for each test is the power peak. The reactor core is approximately cylindrical (diameter of 66 cm) with an active fuel height of about 100 cm. It contains uranium dioxide (UO₂) fuel enriched to 4.8%, arranged in 64 fuel assemblies—each composed of either 5×5 or 4×4 fuel rods—with a compact lattice pitch of 7.62 cm. The core includes eight control rods and one central transient rod, which is ejected to initiate the transient. The fuel is fresh. Several input parameters are provided with associated uncertainties, serving as the basis for the sensitivity analysis to quantify their influence on the power peak. The transient rod acceleration (50.8 cm/s²), nominal reactor power (20 MWth), coolant flow velocity (4.2673 m/s), and system pressure (10.342 MPa) are maintained constant during the experiments.

As reported in the available documentation, only the acceleration and reactivity worth of the transient rod (expressed in dollars) are explicitly specified, while no details are provided regarding its initial position or that of the other control rods. Consequently, it was necessary to implement a computational procedure to determine these positions.

3. ANTARES

ANTARES is a coupled multi-physics platform that integrates PARCS, a three-dimensional neutron kinetics code based on nodal diffusion solvers and a multi-parameter cross-section library—with CATHARE-3 [9], a system thermal-hydraulics code. In this coupling, PARCS provides the spatial and temporal power distribution to CATHARE-3, which in turn supplies updated values of boron concentration, fuel temperature, moderator density, and moderator temperature. All data exchanges between the two codes are managed through internal routines within ANTARES.

In the present study, PARCS was configured using two neutron energy groups: a thermal group (below 0.626 eV) and a fast group (above 0.625 eV). The core was modeled with four radial nodes per assembly.

4. METHODOLOGY

The only information provided by the benchmark specifications concerns the so-called *Initial Reactivity Insertion* of the transient rod, expressed in dollars. Following the interpretation adopted by other authors ([6] and [7]), we have considered this *Initial Reactivity Insertion* to represent the static reactivity worth of the ejected rod.

Several steps are required to establish the rod positions: 1) the control rods are initially inserted into the core to obtain a preliminary estimate of the effective delayed neutron fraction (β_{eff}) and to compute the *Initial Reactivity Insertion* in pcm, with the transient rod withdrawn; 2) the control rod positions are then

adjusted until the core reactivity matches the specified *Initial Reactivity Insertion*; 3) the transient rod is subsequently inserted to achieve a critical state; 4) finally, its motion is computed assuming a constant acceleration, as defined in the benchmark specifications.

About the time step employed during the transient, a value of 0.1 ms was found to provide a reasonable balance between accuracy and computational efficiency.

5. TEST 60

The test is initiated at very low-power level (5E-5 MW). For the transient computation, it was determined that an axial mesh size of 1.26 cm (80 nodes) for PARCS and 3.37 cm (30 nodes) for CATHARE provides adequate numerical stability and accuracy of the results.

Test 60 is characterized by the specifications summarized in Table I.

Table I: Test 60 - Specifications and experimental results

Power	Inlet Primary Coolant Temp. (°C)	Initial Reactivity Insertion (\$)	Power Peak (MW)	Time to Peak Power (s)	Max Clad Temperature Rise (°C)
5.0e-5 MW	260 ± 2.22	1.23 ± 0.05	410 ± 41	0.227	24.44 ± 2.22

The computed control and transient rod positions, along with the main transient results, are presented in Table II. All rod positions are measured from the bottom of the fuel. The differences with respect to experimental data are shown in *italic* and generally fall within the experimental uncertainty range.

Table II: Test 60 - Antares Results

Transient Rod Position (cm)	Control Rod Position (cm)	Beta effective (pcm)	Power Peak (MW)	Time to Peak Power (s)	Max Clad Temperature Rise (°C)
68.125	57.87	754.2	453.4 <i>(+43 ± 41)</i>	0.268 <i>(+0.041)</i>	21.58 <i>(-2.86 ± 2.22)</i>

5.1. Sensitivity Analysis: Effective Temperature

All preceding calculations were performed using Rowlands' model for the effective temperature [8]:

$$T_{eff} = \frac{4}{9}T_{center} + \frac{5}{9}T_{surface}$$

with T_{center} = temperature in the center of the pellet, $T_{surface}$ = temperature at the surface pellet.

The same transient was also simulated using two alternative models of the effective temperature: (i) $T_{eff}=T_c$ and (ii) $T_{eff}=T_s$. In this case, because of the initially uniform temperature distribution within the pellet—resulting from the nearly zero steady-state power—the choice of any effective temperature model does not affect the computed control rod positions.

Figure 1 illustrates the power evolution during the nominal transient (Rowlands) and the transients with $T_{eff}=T_c$ and $T_{eff}=T_s$, including a zoom around the power peak:

Figure 1. Test 60: Impact of effective temperature model

Changing the model of the effective temperature results in a variation of approximately 3–4% in the power peak. For test 60, this is the maximum influence that the choice of T_{eff} can have on the power peak value. It is worth noting that with $T_{eff}=T_c$ the power peak is higher than those obtained using the Rowlands or surface temperature models. This behavior is attributed to the reduced Doppler reactivity feedback, since initiating the transient with a higher temperature leads to a smaller temperature increase.

5.2. Sensitivity Analysis: Uncertainties in Input Data

Two input parameters are associated with experimental uncertainties: the inlet coolant temperature and the initial reactivity insertion. To assess their impact, the transients were computed using both the maximum and minimum values of these parameters. Our calculations indicate that variations in the inlet coolant temperature have a negligible effect on the transient behavior. To evaluate the influence of the maximum and minimum values of the initial reactivity insertion, the control and transient rod positions were recalculated, as summarized in Table III:

Table III: Test 60 - Rods Positions

Initial Reactivity Insertion (β)	Control Rod Position (cm)	Transient Rod Position (cm)
1.18 β	58.01	67.67
1.23 β (reference)	57.87	68.13
1.28 β	57.74	68.55

The resulting transients are presented in Figure 2 (left), together with the experimental transient (Exp_t60_MW). The curve labeled Ref_MW corresponds to the nominal case:

Figure 2. Test 60: Impact of the Reactivity Insertion uncertainty.

As expected for a small reactor such as SPERT, the results show a strong sensitivity of the transient response to the reactivity insertion. Increasing the insertion to 1.28 \$ raises the power peak by around 220 MW and advances the time to peak by approximately 0.03 s, whereas reducing it to 1.18 \$ decreases the peak by around 170 MW and delays it by about 0.04 s. Although the variations in rod position appear small—some millimeters—their impact on the power peak is substantial. This strong effect is attributed to the high sensitivity of the core reactivity to the transient rod position near criticality: a displacement of approximately 1 cm corresponds to about 0.1 \$ (≈ 75 pcm) of rod worth (see Figure 2, right).

5.3. Analysis

This test 60 has been simulated (for what we know) by two other research teams. Figure 3 shows the results we have found in [6] and [7]:

Figure 3. Test 60: Results comparison

The calculated power peak is in reasonable agreement with the experimental observation: 453 MW vs the experimental 410 ± 41 MW. All the simulated cases tend to overestimate, to varying degrees, the maximum power and the time to power peak. These discrepancies still need to be investigated in greater depth. The model of the effective fuel temperature introduces a modest variation—on the order of 3–4%—in the power peak. However, the uncertainty in the initial reactivity insertion has a substantial influence, producing deviations of approximately $[-170; +220]$ MW ($\approx 50\%$) in the power peak and significantly altering the time to reach that peak.

6. TEST 86

The test begins at a high-power level (19 MW, corresponding to 95% of the nominal power). The pronounced axial power gradient justifies the increase in the number of axial meshes to 60 (1.68 cm) in CATHARE, whereas in PARCS, 80 meshes (1.26 cm) were still sufficient to achieve adequate spatial resolution. The specifications of this test are in Table IV:

Table IV: Test 86 - Specifications and experimental Results

Power (MW)	Inlet Primary Coolant Temp. (°C)	Initial Reactivity Insertion (\$)	Power Peak (MW)	Time to Peak Power (s)	Max Clad Temp. (°C)
19 ± 1	261.11 ± 2.22	1.17 ± 0.05	610 ± 60	0.110 ± 0.005	315.55 ± 5.55

The control and transient rods positions and the results of the transient are presented in Table V:

Table V: Test 86 - Antares Results

Transient Rod Position (cm)	Control Rod Position (cm)	Beta effective (pcm)	Power Peak (MW)	Time to Peak Power (s)	Max Clad Temp. (°C)
64.933	53.1426	754.2	439.4 (+171 ± 60)	0.126 (+0.016)	307.54 (-8.01 ± 5.55)

6.1. Sensitivity Analysis: Effective Temperature

In this case, at full power, modifying the model of the effective temperature in the steady state results in a change in the control rod positions and, consequently, alters the transient behavior. To avoid this effect, we chose to keep the control rod positions fixed and to impose zero reactivity at the beginning of the transient by adjusting the total production cross section, using one of the penalty techniques available in ANTARES [1]. Figure 4 presents the experimental results (Power_Exp), the nominal transient (Row_MW), and the transients calculated using the effective temperature equal to the central temperature ($T_{eff} = T_{c_MW}$) and the surface temperature ($T_{eff} = T_{s_MW}$), a zoomed-in view around the power peak:

Figure 4. Test 86: Impact of effective temperature model

The effect on the power peak is significant, particularly when $T_{eff} = T_c$ (an increase of approximately 55%). The observed increase in the power peak for $T_{eff} = T_c$ can be explained by the reduced Doppler reactivity loss, which results from the smaller temperature rise.

6.2. Sensitivity Analysis: Uncertainties in Input Data

Once again, the modification of the inlet temperature has a negligible effect on the power peak. The uncertainty in the steady-state power (± 1 MW—complete results are not shown here due to space limitations) leads to a variation of approximately 2% in the power peak. To obtain this result, the entire procedure for calculating the control rod positions was repeated.

To assess the impact of the initial reactivity insertion uncertainty, the control rod positions were recalculated for each value of the initial reactivity. The corresponding positions are reported in Table VI.

Table VI: Test 86 - Sensitivity Analysis, Rods' Positions vs Transient Rod Uncertainty

Initial Reactivity Insertion ($\$$)	Control Rod Position (cm)	Transient Rod Position (cm)
1.12 $\$$	53.30	64.22
1.17 $\$$ (reference)	53.14	64.93
1.22 $\$$	52.98	65.15

The transients are plotted in Figure 5 (left):

Figure 5. Test 86: Impact of the Reactivity Insertion uncertainty

The variation in the control rod positions results in a change of approximately 100 MW in the power peak, while the time to peak remains nearly unaffected. Once again, the large differences observed in the power peak, despite the small variations in the control rod positions, are attributed to the strong sensitivity of the transient rod worth to the transient rod position (Figure 5, right).

6.3. Analysis

To the best of our knowledge, Test 86 has also been simulated by two other research teams. Figure 6 presents the curves reported in references [4] and [5]:

Figure 6. Test 86: Results comparison

Although the power peak occurs at nearly the same time as in the experimental transient, its magnitude is underestimated (more analysis in the future). Both the model of the effective temperature and the transient rod worth represent significant sources of uncertainty affecting the power peak.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In the initial phase of using the SPERT experiments to validate fast transients simulated with ANTARES (employing a cross-section library provided by the University of Michigan), we performed a sensitivity analysis to determine the necessary level of accuracy for this type of simulation. This analysis underscores the critical importance of accurately calculating control rod positions, as the power peak exhibits strong sensitivity to the transient rod worth. Moreover, uncertainties related to the initial reactivity insertion and the model of the effective temperature can significantly influence the results and must be carefully accounted for in the analysis.

The next phase of our work will involve generating a cross-section library using CASMO5 and simulating additional SPERT test cases.

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REFERENCES

- [1] F. Dubois, M. Forestier, G. Girault, J.C. Jaboulay, F. Jacq, A. Sargeni, "ANTARES: A New IRSN Computational Chain for Safety Analysis", Proceedings of PHYSOR 2022, American Nuclear Society, Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, USA, doi.org/10.13182/PHYSOR22-37270
- [2] T. Albagami et al., "TVA Watts Bar Unit 1 Multi-Physics Multi-Cycle Depletion Benchmark", NEA/EGMPEBV/DOC (2022), Version 2.3.3.
- [3] F. Bernard, S. Bonthoux, M. Forestier, A. Sargeni, J. Taforeau, 2025: First Steps of the ANTARES Validation for Steady States with TVA Watts Bar Unit 1 Cycle 1 Benchmark, Nuclear Science and Engineering, DOI: 10.1080/00295639.2025.253029
- [4] J. Dugone editor, "SPERT III Reactor Facility. E-Core Revision", IDO-17036, US Atomic Energy Commission, 1965
- [5] R.K. McCardell, D.I. Herborn, J.E. Houghtaling, "Reactivity Accident Test Results and Analysis for the SPERT III E-core -- A small, oxide-fueled, pressurized-water reactor", IDO 17281, US Atomic Energy Commission, 1969
- [6] T. Fujita, T. Sakai, (2019), "Analysis of the SPERT-III E-Core Experiment using CASMO5/TRACE/PARCS based on JENDL-4.0 end ENDF/B-VII.1", Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology, 553-771, DOI: 10.1080/00223131.2019.1598306
- [7] W.C. Dawn, G. Grandi, T. Bahadir, "Initial Validation of SIMULATE5-K and CMS5 reactor Modeling Suite with the S-III Experiment", Proceeding of PHYSOR 2024, American Nuclear Society, San Francisco, California, USA, doi.org/10.13182/PHYSOR24-43302
- [8] G. Rowlands, "Resonance absorption and non-uniform temperature distribution", Reactor Science and Technology (Journal of Nuclear Energy Parts A/B), 1962, 16, pp. 235-236, Pergamon Press Ltd
- [9] R. Prea, P. Fillion, L. Matteo, G. Mauger, A. Mekkas. "CATHARE-3 V2.1: The new industrial version of the CATHARE code". ATH'20 Advances in Thermal Hydraulics 2020, Oct 2020, Palaiseau, France. <https://www.ans.org/pubs/proceedings/article-49142/>. (cea-04087378)